

Effect of Reinforcement Material on Fatigue Characteristics of Trans-tibial Prosthetic Socket with PMMA Matrix

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Abstract

In this work, Five varieties of reinforcing materials (fibers and particles) were each laminated separately with PMMA matrix used for manufacturing trans-tibial prosthetic socket and fabricated using vacuum molding technique. The tensile and fatigue properties of Five trans-tibial prosthetic sockets were studied experimentally, theoretically and by using finite element method (Ansys-11). Results showed that the weakest laminate based on mechanical strength (Tensile strength and Fatigue limit) was [PMMA+8Perlon layers] composite and the highest mechanical strength was found in [PMMA+(3Perlon+2(Carbon +Glass))+3Perlon layers] composite. Results of finite element method and theoretical calculation also indicate that the [PMMA+(3Perlon+2(Carbon +Glass))+3Perlon layers] composite has the highest safety factor and the lowest values of both (deformation and failure index) making that composite the best candidate to give better fatigue characteristics of trans-tibial prosthetic socket.

Key words: Prosthetic, Trans-tibial, Fatigue, Ansys, Laminated composites.

I. INTRODUCTION

Prosthesis An artificial device used to replace a missing body part, such as a limb, tooth, eye, or heart valve. For optimal prosthetic performances, the socket must be facilitate motion. Forces, generated by the residual limb through gait motion, must be efficiently transmitted for the limb to the prosthesis; thus, any relative motion exhibited between the residual limb and the socket will challenge successful ambulation, thereby increasing fatigue and discomfort. Patients expect to receive prosthesis with proper fit, ultimate comfort and functionality. Additionally, the prosthesis must be light weight and cosmetically appealing. Majority of the failure of prosthetic components are fatigue related under cyclic walking loads. Materials and mechanical properties of the prosthetic socket were studied by many investigators. T.A. Current et.al. quantified the structural strength of various trans-tibial composite sockets. Five different reinforcement materials and two resin type were used to construct the sockets [1]. M. Zhang and C. Roberts, predicted Interface pressures and shear stresses between a below-knee residual limb and prosthetic socket using finite element analyses which were then compared with experimental measurements [2]. Sam L. Philips and William Crelius initiate a data base on material

properties of typical laminations used in prosthetic limb sockets, the authors subjected samples of common prosthetic laminations to tensile and bending tests. Eight varieties of lay-up materials (fibers) were each laminated separately with one of three common resins (matrix), resulting in 24 combinations of fiber/resin laminates [3]. H. F. Neama, presents analyses for below knee prosthetic socket. Socket stress distribution is performed on three types of sockets, polypropylene (5mm), polypropylene (3mm) and standard laminate (8 layers of nylglass) (3mm) sockets to determine the stress path through the prosthetic socket during gait cycle [4]. S. H. Mohammed investigate the ankle-foot orthoses numerically and experimentally using perlon-carbon-fibers-acrylic materials instead of typical used polypropylene materials [5]. This article reports the effect of materials type on Tensile strength and Fatigue characteristics of trans-tibial prosthetic socket, By quantifying socket's structural strength (Experimentally, Numerically and Theoretically) of five different reinforcement [perlon fiber, carbon fiber, glass fiber, (carbon+glass) fiber and (carbon+glass) fiber+SiO₂ particles] with PMMA matrix.

II. THEORETICAL PART

Theoretical part of this article is based on the following Theories and Criteria:

Goodman relationship

An empirical relationships have been devised to describe the relationship between fatigue limit and mean stress [6]:

$$\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_e} + \frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_{ts}} = 1$$

Where:

σ_a = stress amplitude or Von Mises equivalent stress.

σ_e = stress at fatigue limit (endurance limit).

σ_m = mean stress.

σ_{ts} = Ultimate Tensile Strength.

Strain Energy criterion

The strain energy may be used as a fatigue failure criterion for fiber-reinforced materials. Since this parameter does not rely on the different failure modes obtained in composites, it gives equally good results independent of the failure mechanism [7]. The area under the stress-strain graph is the strain energy per unit volume as shown in the following equation [8]:

$$\Delta W = \frac{1}{2} \sigma \epsilon$$

Where:

ΔW = Strain energy (Joul/mm³).
 σ = stress value (MPa).
 ϵ = strain value (%).

Von Mises Equivalent stress

The Von Mises stresses "allow the most complicated stress situation to be represented by a single quantity" [6] and can be calculated by the following equation[9]:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \left[\frac{1}{2} \left[(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 + 6(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2) \right] \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Where:

σ_{eq} = Von Mises equivalent stress
 σ_x = principal normal stress in x-direction.
 σ_y = principal normal stress in y-direction.
 σ_z = principal normal stress in z-direction.
 τ_{xy} = shear stress in xy-plane.
 τ_{yz} = shear stress in yz-plane.
 τ_{zx} = shear stress in zx-plane.

Maximum Shear

The mathematical representation of maximum shear stress τ_{max} [6], is:

$$\tau_{max} = \frac{\sigma_x - \sigma_z}{2}$$

Factor of Safety

The maximum equivalent stress failure theory states that a particular combination of principal stresses causes failure if the maximum equivalent stress (σ_e) in a structure equals or exceeds a specific stress limit (σ_{ts}). Therefore the expression the theory as a design goal[6]:

$$\frac{\sigma_e}{\sigma_{ts}} < 1$$

So, equation of safety factor can be written as follows:

$$\text{Safety Factor}(SF) = \frac{\text{Tensile Stress}(\sigma_{ts})}{\text{endurance Stress}(\sigma_e)}$$

Fatigue Ratio (R_f)

The fatigue ratio (R_f) is the ratio of the endurance limit to the tensile stress[10]:

$$\text{Fatigue Ratio}(R_f) = \frac{\text{Endurance limit}(\sigma_e)}{\text{Tensile Strength}(\sigma_{ts})}$$

Failure Index(k)

It can be calculated from the following equation[11]:

$$\text{Failure Index}(k) = \frac{\text{Von Mises Stress}}{\text{Experimental Failure strength}}$$

III. EXPERIMENTAL PART

The materials of the socket chosen were randomly laminated (This means that the material is isotropic) by vacuum cleaning method. Table(1) represents the contents of five lamination used in this work.

The Tensile tests were carried out on a Instron universal testing machine at ambient temperature. The standard specimens are cut according to ASTM D638 [12]. The crosshead speed was 5mm/min. The mechanical properties (Tensile strength and Young's modulus) of the composite used in this work are determined from stress-strain curve while Poisson's ratio was calculated theoretically by Rule of mixture [13], table(2) contains

physical and mechanical properties of the five composites of this work.

Also the Fatigue tests were carried out on Alternating Bending fatigue machine of flat specimens at ambient temperature. The standard specimens are cut according to dimension given in the machine's manual [14] with 100 mm length*10 mm width with varying thickness.

IV. Finite Element Analysis (FEM)

Finite Element Analysis provides (Fatigue Life, Fatigue Factor of Safety, Equivalent Alternating Stress (Von Mises Stresses), Maximum total Deformation, Maximum Shear Stress) distribution of the simulated prosthetic socket of 75.5 kg in body mass.

The model of socket was plotted in AutoCAD program after cutting a positive mold made of gypsum of tran-tibial amputee into horizontal discs then measuring and recording its (x, y, z) dimension and finally exporting the socket's geometry to Ansys-11 work bench. As shown in fig.(1 a, b, c.).The socket is analyzed at the most extreme load conditions, which exist at heel strike in Gait cycle. Pressures values listed in table (3) were applied on sockets plane shown in fig.(1c) [15].

The Ansys (11) package is used here for this type of analysis, the three-dimensional element is SOLID 185 as in Fig.(2) is used for 3-D modeling of solid structures. It is defined by eight nodes having three degrees of freedom at each node: translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions. The element has plasticity, hyper elasticity, stress stiffening, creep, large deflection, and large strain [6]. Fig.(3) represents the mesh generation of the composite sockets.

V. RESULTS and DISSCUSSION

A. Experimental results

1)Results of tension test:

Results of Young's modulus(E), Stiffness, Elongation, and Ultimate tensile strength derived from tension test are listed in Table (2)

In general, it is noted that the Young's modulus (E), Stiffness and Ultimate tensile strength of Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite were the highest. In addition, it is noted that the Elongation of the Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite was higher than other composite materials, which indicates that addition of this reinforcement to PMMA increases its elasticity.

2)Stress-No. of Cycles (S-N) Results:

The results of all fatigue tests carried out at various reinforcement are graphically displayed in the form of S-N curves shown in fig.(4) these curves were obtained by curve fitting the experimental data of fatigue test, using logarithmic formula [16].

The log equations which express the fatigue behavior of the five composite materials and its relative correlation coefficient (R^2) are given in table (4).

It is evident from fig.(4) that for all classes of laminates, reinforcement type had a pronounced influence on their fatigue resistance. When comparing the behavior of composites, the fatigue limit was significantly increased in Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite, whereas, a severe reduction in fatigue limit is noted in Perlon reinforced composite.

The fatigue strength of the tested materials was taken at No. of Cycle of 10^6 [17]. Fatigue limit of Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite increase as much as eight orders of

magnitude as compared to Perlon reinforced composite as shown in fig.(5).

In general, the fatigue limit of materials is proportional to its tensile strength[18]; hence materials with higher ultimate tensile strength possess higher fatigue limit. This in fact, is in good agreement with the result.

3) Strain Energy-No. of Cycles Results:

The strain energy for the five composites and plotted in fig.(6) and strain energy limit in fig.(7). It can be seen that Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite had the highest strain energy and that is logical since its stress and strain value are high which means that this composite material have the ability to store a large amount of energy before damage and failure take place. It can be seen that the strain energy limit of Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforcing composite was higher than carbon reinforced composite, Glass reinforced composite, Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) + SiO₂ particles reinforced composite and Perlon reinforced composite by (19, 16.4, 5.6 and 35.7) time respectively.

B. Numerical Results:

1) Fatigue Life:

Numerical results of Fatigue Life shows the available life for a given fatigue analysis. Counter plots shown in fig.(8) were used to display the overall distribution of life throughout the socket for each type of composite used in this study. In stress life analysis with constant amplitude, if the equivalent alternating stress is lower than the lowest alternating stress defined in the S-N curve, the life at that point will be used [6].

2) Fatigue factor of Safety:

Counter plots of the factor of safety with respect to fatigue failure at a given design life. In Ansys, Maximum factor of safety displayed is 15, values less than one indicate failure before the design life has been reached [6]. It can be noticed in fig.(9) the distribution of safe and unsafe regions of one of the five composite. Minimum safety factor of each composites were recorded in the mentioned fig.(9) above where it can be seen that Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite had the highest safety factor of (6.7705) and Perlon reinforced composite had the lowest safety factor of (0.6589). It is obvious that all materials are safe except Perlon reinforced composite because it's safety factor value less than 1 which indicate that failure will take place before the design life reached.

3) Equivalent alternating stress (Von Mises stresses):

Equivalent alternating stress is the stress used to query the fatigue S-N curve after accounting for fatigue loading type, R-ratio effects and any other factor in fatigue analysis. Equivalent alternating stress is the last calculated quantity before determining the fatigue life [6]. The result is useful for cases where the design criteria is based on an equivalent alternating stress as specified by the fatigue analyst. Fig.(10) shows contour plots of one of the five composites which display the overall distribution of the Von Mises stresses throughout the material, as well as determine the approximate location and value of the maximum Von Mises stresses.

4) Maximum total Deformation:

Fig.(11) Shows that the maximum deformation for one of five composites. Where it can be seen that Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite had the smallest amount of deformation

with (1.5276mm) Perlon reinforced composite had the highest amount of deformation with (2.8418mm).

5) Maximum Shear Stress:

Fig.(12) shows contour plots of one of the five composites which display the overall distribution of the Maximum Shear Stress throughout the material, as well as determine the approximate location and value of the Maximum Shear Stress.

C. Theoretical Results:

1) Fatigue Ratio (R_f)

As shown in fig.(13) fatigue ratio of both carbon reinforced composite and Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite were the highest. Since, both Fatigue Limit and Tensile strength of Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite was the highest between the five composites, so, this composite consider to possess the best fatigue ratio (R_f) which coincidence with the Experimental result.

2) Factor of Safety (SF):

As shown in fig.(14), Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite gave the highest Safety Factor among all five composites and Perlon reinforced composite had the lowest amount of Safety Factor.

3) Failure Index (K)

As shown in fig.(15), Hybrid (Carbon+Glass) reinforced composite gave the lowest Failure Index among all five composites and Perlon reinforced composite had the highest amount of Failure Index.

CONCLUSION

All the Experimental, Numerical and Theoretical results proved that Hybrid (Glass+Carbon) Reinforcement with PMMA matrix was the best composite could be used to give the optimum Tension and Fatigue Characteristics for Trans-tibial prosthetic socket.

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Table 1.
Laminated composites used in this work

No.of Lamination	Lamination Resin type	Fiber stockinet layers/ Powder reinforcement
Lamination 1	PMMA	(8perlon)
Lamination 2		(3perlon+2carbon fiber+3 perlon)
Lamination 3		(3perlon+2 glass fiber+3 perlon)
Lamination 4		(3perlon+2(carbon + glass)fiber+3 perlon)
Lamination 5		(3perlon+2(carbon + glass)fiber+3 perlon) + 3% (nano+micro) SiO ₂ powder

Table 2.
Mechanical and physical properties of composites used in this work

No.of Lamination	Lamination Resin type	Reinforcement	E(GPa)	Stiffness (N/mm)	Elongation (%)	Tensile Strength(MPa)	Poisson's ratio	density (gm/cm ³)
Lamination 1	PMMA	P	1.5	1080	1.833	12.39	0.3624	1.0594
Lamination 2		C	2.586	1633.33	2.1	38.8	0.332162	1.1368
Lamination 3		G	2.5	1563.158	2.375	20.82	0.33061608	1.3668
Lamination 4		G+C	2.8125	1898.57	2.763	62.7	0.330362	1.3342
Lamination 5		(G+C)+ SiO ₂	1.6	1327.778	5.04	42.94	0.274213	1.6491

Table 3.
Location and average pressure values of heal strike generated in socket[15].

Location	Anterior	posterior	medial	lateral	basal
Average Pressure value (MPa)	0.011655	0.0444075	0.03434	0.045765	0.288

Table 4.
The S-N curves log equations and their relative correlation coefficient .

No.of Lamination	Lamination Resin type	Reinforcement	Curve fitting equation of (S-N)	R ²
Lamination 1	PMMA	P	$\sigma = -1.54222 * \log(N) + 25.8763$	0.914566
Lamination 2		C	$\sigma = -0.76104 * \log(N) + 41.0766$	0.888336
Lamination 3		G	$\sigma = -1.76969 * \log(N) + 36.0201$	0.902739
Lamination 4		G+C	$\sigma = -6.628 * \log(N) + 131.888$	0.963079
Lamination 5		G+C+SiO ₂	$\sigma = -4.53695 * \log(N) + 75.2228$	0.983538

Fig.1 a-positive mold of prosthetic socket. b- discs of positive mold. c-Auto CAD model of prosthetic socket.

Fig.2 Three dimensional element solid 185.

Fig.3 The meshed socket.

Fig.4 The S-N curves of five composites.

Fig.5 The fatigue limit of five composites .

Fig.6 The Strain energy -N curves of five composites.

Fig.7 The Strain energy limit of five composites

Fig.(8) Sample of contours of fatigue life distribution.

Fig.(9) Sample of Contours of Fatigue Safety Factor distribution.

Fig.(10) Sample of Contours of Equivalent Von Mises stress distribution

Fig.(11) Sample of total deformation.

Fig.(12) Sample of max. shear stress.

Fig.13 Fatigue ratio of five composites .

Fig.14 The theoretical safety factor of five composites .

Fig.15 The theoretical Failure Index of five composites .